

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF GREEN COMPOSITE USING BIOMIMETIC MODIFIED LIGNIN

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1 Introduction

The natural polymer lignin, second only to cellulose in natural abundance, is readily available, relatively inexpensive, and is considered a waste product. The annual sales of lignin as a specialty chemical in 1998 amounted to only 1% of the total lignin production [1].

The remaining 99% is burned as part of an energy recovery step or disposed of in waste streams. However, it is very inefficient as a fuel source, producing less than 1/4 of the energy of middle distillate (diesel, jet, and boiler) fuels. Meanwhile, an ever-increasing number of paper mills have become chemical recovery limited, such that if paper production is to be maximized, then the by-product lignin can no longer be used in its traditional role as a fuel[2].

Lignin has enormous potential as a raw material for polymer industries because it is a renewable, nontoxic, commercially available, and low-cost natural resource. In spite of the many years of development efforts, the full potential of lignin has not been fully utilized. Lignin has not been utilized as a raw material in spite of its many advantages because of its brittleness and difficulty to process. Therefore, lignin-based polymer blends have been developed to enhance the thermoplastic behavior of lignin.

However, the amount of lignin incorporation into polymeric materials is generally limited due to the inherent brittleness caused by OH group of the lignin or phase separation due to immiscibility [3]. One of the approaches to utilize lignin as a raw material is to use lignin as a comonomer in

polyurethane or polyester. The incorporation of lignin in various polyurethanes through the alcohol-isocyanate reaction has resulted in improved mechanical properties and higher glass transition temperatures, as compared to polyurethanes without lignin [4-6]. High lignin content (>30%) has resulted in brittle polyurethanes, regardless of the lignin molecular weight and alcohol-to-isocyanate ratio [7].

Considering lignin incorporated in polyesters, the copolymerization of lignin with acid chlorides resulted in rigid polyester materials [8]. Incorporation of lignin in polyesters by co-reaction of the lignin hydroxyl groups with polyethylene glycol and acid chlorides has resulted in elastomeric polyesters due to the soft segment effect of polyethylene glycol [9].

Chemical modification of lignin is a big part of the lignin in the lignin research. Chemical modification of lignin is a method to replace the carboxyl group and hydroxyl group of lignin by alkylation, acylation and Hydroxyalkylation.[10] The theoretical basis for this modification is lignin is exist in the LCC in plants. The discussion about LCC was the long time controversy. But today, LCC has a chemical bond that between the hemicellulose and lignin is established theory . These fact is a very reasonable that the theory of the biosynthesis of lignin also demonstrated by electron microscopy.

Proto lignin form a covalent bond with hemicellulose chemically via a glycoside bond and ether bond in plants. Lignin-carbohydrate has been proposed until now - by combined with glycoside bond with the hydroxyl group of the aromatic ring, combined with ester bond of the side chain and the

ether linkage of the side chain. There is evidence that each was presented. Carbohydrate combined with lignin was proposed L-arabinose, D-xylose and D-galactose. [11]

Two types of reagent were used that have different solubility parameter (SP). And the reagents combined with lignin chemically to mimic that LCC structure. Non-modified lignin have the amphiphilic nature because the hydrophilic hydroxyl groups and hydrophobic benzene ring. [12]

In the case of polymeric materials blend, polymers are blend well that kinds of polymer SP value is close to each other. This is similar to the well-mixed water and alcohol when mixed. If the SP value is very different to the contrary, phase separation occur as the relationship between water and oil. [13]

Two reagents are used in this study. These two types of alkyl chain derivatives had been block the hydroxyl groups of lignin and replace the hydroxyl groups of lignin by a glycoside bond. Also it can make a SP value of modified lignin similar to the SP value for the blending synthetic polymer.

Cellulose is compatible with hemicellulose, and hemicellulose is coupled to lignin with ether bond, glycoside bond and ester bond in the plant fibers. To mimic this, lignin is combined with an alkyl chain that have similar SP value, used as the matrix polymer by glycoside bond. This is similar to the relationship between the cellulose and the LCC

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Lactic acid, Tetrahydrofuran and sulfuric acid used in this study were purchased from Junsei Co., GR grade. The Indulin AT® softwood kraft lignin (SKL) used in this study was purchased from MeadWestvaco Co., North Charleston, South Carolina, USA.

Reagents are started to turn a form of the aliphatic chain by acid catalyst via the ring-opening

polymerization [14,15] and attached to lignin in the early stage. (Fig. 1.)

Chemically modified lignin is blended with Poly Lactic Acid (Tg - 70°C, Mw - 80,000) for matrix. Modified lignin and synthetic polymers are prepared with different weight ratio of 0:100, 20:80, 40:60, 60:40, 80:20, 100:0

Figure 1. Modification of lignin using Lactide and Tetrahydrofuran

2.2 Characterization of modified lignin/ PLA blended matrix

2.2.1 FT-IR

To investigate the chemical properties of lignin and modified lignin, solid-state FTIR spectra for the samples were obtained by FTIR spectrophotometer (Nicolet 6700, Thermo Scientific Inc., USA) using ATR (attenuated total reflectance) technique. FTIR spectra of samples were recorded between 4000-650 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

2.2.2 ¹H-NMR

¹H-NMR spectra is obtained using 400MHz NMR Spectrometer (JeolJNM-LA400 with LFG, JEOL,

JAPAN)

2.2.3 Thermal Properties

A differential scanning calorimeter (DSC-Q1000, TA Instrument Inc., UK) was used to investigate the thermal transition behavior of modified lignin/PLA composites. A total of 4-12 mg of samples were scanned from -80 to 200 °C at the heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹

2.2.4 Mechanical Properties

A universal testing machine (LRXPlus, LLOYD Instruments Inc., UK) was used to investigate the tensile properties of the synthetic polymers and modified lignin/synthetic polymer composites. The tensile test was performed according to ASTM D 638- guidelines with ASTM type V specimens (dumbbell type). Sample thickness was 1.2-1.8 mm and the strain rate was 10 mm min⁻¹. The data were calculated from the average of a minimum of 10 specimens.

3 Results & Discussion

3.1 FT-IR

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra of lignin modified lignin

As shown in Figure 2, FT-IR graph of PLA modified lignin(PLAL) and THF modified lignin(THFL) that there is a difference with the original lignin. PLAL shows remarkable changes in an ester functional group of 1747 cm⁻¹ C=O peak and 1168 cm⁻¹ CO peak had shown very strong that pure lignin had weak signal. This results shows that PLAL has remarkable change, compared with pure lignin.

THF made a lignin more hydrophobic because the OH group of lignin decreased with the content of THF. THF modified lignin spectra shows small peaks in an alcohol functional group 3250 cm⁻¹ OH, 1033 cm⁻¹ CO peak. From this result, the OH groups present in the lignin has been reduced, the portion of benzene ring in lignin is hydrophobic basically, the SP value of overall THF modified lignin approaches hydrophobic.

3.2 1H-NMR

OH group of lignin was reduced significantly in both the THFL and PLAL. (Fig. 3.) This indicates that as the result of supporting the FT-IR, the original lignin is substituted alkyl chain of polymerized modification agent.

Furthermore, the alkyl chain that replace OH group of lignin, they reduce the brittle nature of the lignin was confirmed. OH group of lignin can not exhibit the characteristics of a typical OH.

Because the molecular structure of lignin - aromatic OH group of lignin did not work typical behavior. OH group in the middle of the chain or alkyl chain end do the role of improving the physical properties of the polymer chain flexibility by the active intermolecular interaction, but OH group of lignin is cause of brittleness.

In the case of THFL, mechanism of PTMEG replaced with terminal OH lignin is etherification reaction, the etherification reaction stable as is well known, but the reactivity is low compared to the esterification reaction. Therefore, it can be seen that many remaining OH group of lignin in THFL NMR spectra as compared to PLAL. It can be seen that

from the results of THFL NMR spectra shows the free OH peak is smaller than total amount of the original lignin OH. From this results, THFL becomes hydrophobic than the original lignin.

(a) Lignin

(b) THFL

(c) PLAL

Figure 3. ¹H-NMR spectra of (a)Lignin, (b) THFL and (c) PLAL

PLAL modification is an esterification reaction that had a high reactivity. NMR spectra shows almost of lignin hydroxyl group disappeared by alkyl chain modification. ¹H-NMR Spectra shows evidence of modification that presence of specific PLA signal near 5.0ppm, instead of lignin OH absence. It is a good evidence of alkyl chain modification of lignin. It complements FT-IR spectra.

The results of FT-IR and NMR analysis indicate that the OH groups of lignin had been well replaced with alkyl chains through modification. The modification of lignin was confirmed by FT-IR and NMR data, which showed that the reaction sites of lignin. Shows the concept of modification of lignin shown in Fig. 1., cause of the alkyl chain act as outer shell of lignin, compatibility of alkyl chain between PLA affects the compatibility between PLA and modified lignin can imagine without difficulty.

3.3 DSC analysys of modified lignin

DSC analysis of lignin is shown in the Fig.4 (a). As shown, it can be seen that due to the specific molecular structure of the lignin does not have a specific Tg or Tm. Lignin shows the characteristics of becoming a thermosetting polymer through a process called 'sintering' at approximately 160 ~ 200°C; these properties are also altered by the substitution of the alkyl chain. It is able to know that the thermal properties of modified lignin have changed.

In the case of PLAL, it can be seen to have a Tg at 6.2 °C for low molecular weight PLA chains that used to modification. Low molecular weight PLA, used in the modification with a Tm of about 70°C, but for PLAL, it can be seen that the presence of lignin, crystal formation is inhibited, it has no Tm. In the case of the THFL, it can be seen that the Tm value was not that same as that of the original lignin but 156°C. This Tm occurred because of the decrease in the number of hydrogen bonds in the THFL.

Figure 4. DSC analysis of (a)Lignin, (b) THFL and (c) PLAL

3.4 DSC analysis of Blended matrixes

The DSC analysis shows that phase change of modified lignin and PLA with different blend ratio. (Fig. 5.) However, when the ratio of PLA blends

with different modified lignin, It can be found that the addition of modified lignin, the thermal properties of PLA is changed.

As the amount of THFL increases, Tg of the PLA decreases to gradually at 55.9°C from 64.3°C. This is presumably because the chain flexibility is increased by the THFL is present in the PLA matrix as discussed above NMR analysis. In the case of lignin/PLA blend,[16] or as shown in Fig. 5.(b) PLAL/PLA blend, It can be confirmed that the change of Tg is insignificant.

Figure 5. DSC analysis of (a) THFL/PLA blend and (b) PLAL/PLA blend

Furthermore, it is considered that THFL act as nucleation agent, cause of T_c increases with the amount of THFL. It can be found that the amount of THFL increases, T_c is increased, the proportion of crystall also increases. However, the proportion of the crystall became smaller when the ratio of THFL is more than 60%, it is because THFL itself not able to work as a matrix but greater than the proportion of PLA.

The addition of THFL does not affect the T_m of the PLA matrix. Proportion of THFL increases to more than 40%, see the small melting peak in melting peak before the PLA, is a melting peak of this THFL. It is considered that the compatibility between THFL/PLA is not so good, from shown in Fig. 5.(a), two peak being separated.

As discussed above, It can be can seen that the addition of PLAL affect a little, T_g of PLAL/PLA blends. This is because not affect the intermolecular interaction to have a same linear chain molecular structure, such as a high molecular weight PLA was used as a matrix, low molecular weight PLA chain used in the modification of PLAL. However, in the case of more than 60% of PLAL, shows a sharp decline T_g at 56.2°C from 64.3°C. The reason is that the proportion of PLAL is increased to 60%, matrix-filler relationship became reversed.

As shown in Fig. 5.(b), in the case of up to 40% added with PLAL, shows a behavior does not affect the T_c of the PLA as same as lignin/PLA that are not affect the T_c change[16]. However, in this case it seems to behavior T_c decreases rapidly when PLAL becomes 60% is considered the relationship matrix/filler is reversed, PLAL work as the matrix. This addition ratio is changed to reverse proportion, substances of high molecular weight acts as an filler, an abrupt change in thermal properties as shown by studies on blends of high molecular weight substances and similar molecular structure low molecular weight substances.

Show the behavior of PLAL 40% case T_m to increase gradually, but in PLAL60%, show a sharp decline again, it is because it formed the crystal

structure of other states that compared to PLA crystall, this is the characteristic PLAL-PLA melting peak of this crystall. As shown in Fig. 4.(b), PLAL don't show characteristic T_m , because of this specific character, this unique crystal structure determined when crystals of PLA is generated by PLAL and it called co-crystall[17].

Typically, co-crystal formation occurs between two highly compatible polymers, and the co-crystal generally exhibits an intermediate T_m between the T_m values of the two polymers; moreover, the co-crystal also exhibits distinct physico-chemical properties [18].

3.4 Mechanical Properties

(a) PLAL/PLA

(b) THFL/PLA

Figure 6. Mechanical properties of (a)PLAL-PLA blend and (b)THFL-PLA blend

All of the mechanical properties of PLAL-PLA is decreased. Mechanical properties of 40:60 - PLAL : PLA decreased remarkably, while ones of 20:80 decreased a little. (Fig.6)

In the case of PLAL/PLA blend, shows a sharp decline in physical properties than when the lignin/PLA blend[16]. When the time added THFL or lignin blend with PLA, which did not affects the crystal structure itself but the crystallinity of the PLA, while type and shape of PLA crystal is intact, as described above from DSC analysis, the crystal structure of the PLA is considered that for changing by the added PLAL.

When added THFL40%, decrease in physical properties was less than the 23.2Mpa the strength of the case of adding 40% of the lignin[16], as the intended purpose. In the case of THFL 40%, the tensile strength of THFL/PLA blend shows around 40Mpa. Same as strength, modulus and strain decline was less as compared with the case of PLAL or lignin/PLA blend. It is considered that the result of side chain of THFL reduced the brittleness. In the case of THFL, measurement is not possible excessive amount of THFL60% or more.

4 Conclusion

Modified lignin was analyzed by FT-IR and NMR analysis. DSC analyses of modified lignin were performed to measure the thermal properties and changes thereof of the blends created. DSC analysis was performed to examine the effects of different blending ratios on the thermal properties and compatibility between modified lignin and PLA. The data obtained indicate that lignin was well modified, whereby the physicochemical properties of lignin were significantly altered.

The results of FT-IR and NMR analysis indicate that the OH groups of lignin had been well replaced with alkyl chains through modification. The modification of lignin was confirmed by FT-IR and NMR data, which showed that the reaction sites of lignin.

DSC analyses demonstrated that differences in thermal properties between lignin and modified lignin arose. Furthermore, it was observed that the thermal and physicochemical properties of modified lignin/PLA blend could be adjusted according to the characteristics of the alkyl chains. In addition, lignin showed characteristics of becoming a thermosetting polymer through a process called 'sintering' at approximately 160 ~ 200°C; moreover, these properties could be altered by the substitution of alkyl chains for OH groups.

Properties when adding the THFL is better than PLAL, different from expected result that tensile properties of the PLAL/PLA blend is better physical properties cause of good compatibility. This is because forming a co-crystal, crystals of PLA that was used as a matrix, generated cause of outer chain of PLAL is low molecular weight PLA[17]. As a result, the physical properties of the resulting blends were limited by alkyl chain of modified lignin.

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